

MODELING SMART HOME SYSTEM CONFIGURATIONS BASED
ON WIRELESS NETWORKS

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Abstract. This article describes the research of smart home system configurations based on wireless networks. The goal of the research is to study the interaction of smart devices with the supporting communication methods like Wi-Fi and ZigBee with emphasis on the centralized control and secure data exchange. A virtual smart home system was built and tested using Cisco Packet Tracer software to eliminate the need for real components. The study concentrates on methods of configuration, communication flows of devices, and performance evaluation in simulation. Emphasis is also placed on system-modeled parameters such as flexibility, dependability, and energy consumption. The proposed architecture supports dynamic device association and offers increased flexibility for topology changes. Simulation verifies that wireless networks are reliable and robust for managing smart home functions. The results help develop fence-less secure control systems for remote wireless control services in homes. This work forms a basis for further work in smart spaces based on the internet of things.

Keywords: SHS, WSN, IoT, network topology, protocols, remote monitoring, real-time, embedded systems, simulation and modeling

Introduction

Thanks to the rapid development of modern technologies and digital systems, human life is becoming more convenient and safer. One of such innovative solutions is the smart home system. A smart home system (SHS) is a dwelling

equipped with intelligent technologies designed to provide personalized services to its users. To facilitate the implementation and adoption of smart home technology, it is important to study the perspectives of users and the current state of smart homes. Given the rapid development of the literature in this area, there is a need to review the existing information. SHS is an integrated solution that allows you to automate or remotely control all the main devices in a home, including lighting, heating, cooling, security, appliances, and other systems. These systems provide the user with the ability to control their home from a single point, which ensures convenience and efficiency [1, 2].

Nowadays, the digitalization and automation of modern housing infrastructure is developing rapidly. In particular, smart home systems based on wireless networks are distinguished by their ability to make everyday life easier, save energy, increase security, and allow remote control. Modeling the efficient operation and reliable configuration of these systems is of great importance in expanding their practical application. By analyzing and optimizing the system configuration based on simulation, it is possible to predict the interoperability of devices, network load, and energy efficiency. Therefore, modeling smart home systems is one of the important and relevant areas of today's telecommunications and information technologies [2].

2. Organizing the SHS in virtual environments

Wireless communication enables devices in a smart home network to communicate with each other and with external networks, laying the foundation for Internet of Things (IoT) systems. Technologies such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, ZigBee, Z-Wave, and Thread are playing a key role in making smart homes more connected and user-friendly. These technologies not only facilitate communication between devices, but also support advanced features such as remote control, automation, and data analytics, thereby contributing to the overall efficiency and intelligence of smart home ecosystems [3].

The following elements were used in the design of the smart home: home gateway, smart lamp, temperature meter, smart fan, smoke detector, smart water meter, smart door, smart coffee maker, smart window, smart alarm, garage door, smart sprinkler, thermostat, smart battery, smart solar panel, MCU, heating unit.

Smart home devices can be controlled remotely from any home computer. All smart devices connect to the Home Gateway, which allows users to control the devices via a web interface. This can be done using tablets, smartphones, laptops or desktop computers [5].

To do this, you need to follow the following sequence:

Fig.2. The process of connecting to a smart home interface

Fig.3. Interface structure

The role of the MCU device in a smart home system is extremely important. It monitors smoke or carbon dioxide levels in real time, and takes quick action when they exceed the required level. Since this system is based on fog computing

technology, all decisions are made locally and actions are taken without delay. As a result, user safety is ensured and dependence on the Internet is reduced. This automated approach through the MCU is of great importance not only in maintaining air quality, but also in protecting human life [6].

Fig.4. Cooling system in the dormitory

This process is aimed at constantly monitoring the air temperature in the bedroom and maintaining a comfortable environment. If the air temperature in the room exceeds 15°C, the ceiling fan automatically starts at medium speed. When the temperature drops back to 15°C, the fan turns off automatically [7, 8]. This ensures energy efficiency and brings the temperature back to equilibrium without user intervention.

Conclusion

In this article, a smart home system configured on wireless networks was modeled and analyzed through simulation in Cisco Packet Tracer. The simulation model showed that different devices - including smart lighting, temperature and water level sensors, smoke detectors, doors, windows, and household appliances can be managed by linking them to a centralized IoT server. Central to the system is a microcontroller (MCU), which connects wirelessly to all devices. Users can

observe and control the status of all household devices in real time via the web interface [8].

Throughout the simulation, the features of contemporary wireless communication technologies including Zigbee, Z-Wave, BLE, Wi-Fi, LoRa, and NB-IoT were examined and analyzed. The findings indicated that low-power, dependable protocols like Zigbee and Z-Wave are ideal for short-range and stable residential networks. Wi-Fi and LoRa prove to be more effective in scenarios that demand long-range and high bandwidth capabilities. NB-IoT technology is deemed appropriate for devices needing slow yet consistent monitoring, such as water meters and smoke detectors.

The system is characterized by modularity, flexibility, and remote control capabilities. Through a model created in Cisco Packet Tracer, the user can interactively monitor the status of devices, configure automatic response mechanisms, and monitor security conditions. This creates a reliable foundation for the real-world application of smart home technologies.

References

1. G. Vats, S. Tanwar and P. K. Sharma, "A Simulation-Based Analysis of IoT Security Architecture in Smart Homes," 2024 International Conference on Computing, Sciences and Communications (ICCSC), Ghaziabad, India, 2024, pp. 1-4.
2. M. Khan, J. Seo and D. Kim, "Modeling of Intelligent Sensor Duty Cycling for Smart Home Automation," in IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 2412-2421, July 2022
3. Liangxu Sun et al., "Comparison between physical devices and simulator software for Cisco network technology teaching", 2013 8th International Conference on Computer Science & Education, 2013.

4. A. Raza et al., "A Home Automation Through Android Mobile App By Using Arduino UNO," 2020 IEEE 23rd International Multitopic Conference (INMIC), Bahawalpur, Pakistan, 2020, pp. 1-6
5. B. Ratnala, T. Anuradha, V. Maddali and H. V. Chintalapudi, "Designing Smart Room Using Cisco Packet Tracer Simulator," 2023 5th International Conference on Smart Systems and Inventive Technology (ICSSIT), Tirunelveli, India, 2023, pp. 183-188
6. M. Assim and A. Al-Omary, "Design and Implementation of Smart Home using WSN and IoT Technologies," 2020 International Conference on Innovation and Intelligence for Informatics, Computing and Technologies (3ICT), Sakheer, Bahrain, 2020, pp. 1-6
7. P. Praveen Kumar, M. Krishna and M. Ramprakash, "Design and Implementation of Smart Home using Cisco Packet Tracer Simulator 7.2", International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering, vol. 8, no. 11, pp. 107-111, 2019.
8. S. Imran Hussain, S. Varshini and V. Vishweshwaran, "Intelligent Room Automation with IoT Integration: A Cisco Packet Tracer Simulation for Enhanced User Experience," 2023 3rd International Conference on Innovative Mechanisms for Industry Applications (ICIMIA), Bengaluru, India, 2023, pp. 78-83

